

PSP 6022 RESIN : A MATRIX FOR THERMOSTABLE, FIRE RESISTANT, HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPOSITE MATERIALS WITH EPOXY TYPE MANUFACTURING METHODS

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PSP 6022 is a heterocyclic aromatic high performance resin for composite materials, easily prepared from common products, with a potential low cost. It can be used for impregnation of various fibers without solvent or, what is outstanding for a thermostable resin, with non polar low boiling point solvents like MEK, allowing manufacturing of thick laminates (more than 3 mm) with very low levels of voids.

An autoclave moulding at 200°C has been found to be effective in curing high performance carbon reinforced PSP 6022, with room temperature mechanical properties close to that of unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates. Post cure at 225°C results in high thermomechanical properties, with interlaminar shear strength of about 55 MPa at 300°C for T 300/6022 laminates.

CARBON/6022 composite materials cured at 200°C are stable during more than 1500h at 250°C, with shear strength and flexural properties retention of at least 50% at 20°C and with high mechanical properties at 250°C.

Moisture resistance is quite impressive : there is less than 15% loss in shear strength at 20°C or 200°C after 1000h exposure of non post-cured T 300/6022 in boiling water.

The outstanding low flammability, low smoke emission and very low toxicity of high char yield PSP 6022 resin should account for an active interest in the use of reinforced PSP 6022 in aircrafts, being a way to resolve the problems occurring with epoxy resins, which cannot prevent in fire environment the release of free-floating carbon/graphite filaments, giving a potential hazard to electrical machinery.

1 - INTRODUCTION

The development, during the fifties and the sixties, of high strength and high modulus carbon fibers, resulted in applications and growing uses in military and commercial aircrafts, and in a lot of consumer products like skis, fishing rods, golf clubs,...

The fibers are binded with a resin, generally an epoxy system, and the composite materials have evident benefits : higher strength, lighter weight, energy savings. But these benefits are not always so easy to reach ; carbon fibers, like boron fibers or other high modulus fibers are now of high quality, with a quite good consistency, but it seems that the matrixes have to be improved in order to attain and maintain high specific properties with such reinforcements, for use for example in parts where high temperature capability is required, like in supersonic aircrafts, missiles, engines, with the ever critical humidity resistance and fire resistance.

Polyesters, phenolics and epoxies are largely used but are inadequate for high performance laminates in such environments. Polyimides work well in high temperatures, but their processing parameters, with curing at 316°C under 2 to 7 MPa, and their price, are unfavourable. The needs may be presented like the following.

- Resin : low cost , easy synthesis, low toxicity
- Impregnation : easy in both solvent and non solvent processes
- Prepregs : long shelf life
- Curing : like for epoxy, in autoclave at 200°C under 0,7 to 1 MPa
- Composite : high performances in terms of mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties, thermal aging, chemical and moisture resistance, flammability properties.

PSP 6022 resins seem to meet all these requirements. Conceived some years ago in the ONERA synthesis and composite materials laboratories, investigated and modified by SNPE for industrial use, the PSP type resins are thermostable systems which have been produced in pilot scale by SNPE for 2 years, and have been used in industrial impregnation of unidirectional carbon twelve inches tapes, and carbon, glass, or silica fabrics, by SNPE and other prepreggers. Laminating is being studied by SNPE, IRCHA and SNIAS in France; Composites Horizons in the USA*, and laminates are under evaluation in most of aerospace companies, as well in Europe as in the USA.

2 - PSP 6022 RESIN

PSP (polystyrylpyridines) are aromatic heterocyclic polymers, synthesised by condensation of aromatic aldehydes with methylated derivatives of pyridine. Typical properties of PSP neat resins are summarized in table 1

(*) - This work was supported under contracts or subcontracts from SNPE DRET, STPE or DTEn.

The wholly aromatic structure results in a high level of thermostability and flame resistance.

Condensation may be stopped easily, in order to make prepolymers usable for impregnation or injection, or to make powders. There are 3 currently available resins, but other formulations can be prepared depending on the applications.

PSP 6022 M is a solution of about 200 mPas with 70 % solid content in MEK, and this is an outstanding characteristic for a thermostable resin to be fully soluble in pure MEK, without any polar solvent like DMF or NMP which result in lowering mechanical properties of carbon reinforced composites unless curing at more than 300°C. PSP 6022 N was the same prepolymer in MEK/propanol solvent, but with non reactive bad odor volatiles which have been removed from PSP 6022M.

PSP 6022 P is a non solvent system for non solvent impregnation or injection, with a viscosity of about 1000 to 3000 mPas at 100 °C.

PSP 6022PC is a powder, which may be used for injection at 180 °C or to make chopped fibers reinforced molding compounds.

The resins, being easily prepared from common products, are of low cost even in pilot scale, compared with high performance polyimides, and might be no more expensive than epoxy resins for extensive uses.

PSP 6022 M, P and PC thermal aging properties have been measured on neat resin : weight loss in air is only 2 % after 1 200 hrs at 250 °C. Pyrolysis of PSP resin in non oxidative atmosphere gives a high char yield, of about 65 % at 1000°C, with good mechanical resistance. A 90° coefficient of thermal expansion of 45.10^{-6} /°C has been measured on T300/6022 unidirectional laminate. There was no transition before 330°C and decomposition did not occur before 450°C, with a cure cycle of 4 hrs 200 °C and 2 hrs 250 °C under 1MPa, without any postcure.

Toxicity of 6022 M and 6022 P prepolymers is very low : intragastric lethal dose 50 is more than 6 ml/kg, measured on Wistar rats, and Draize scores 0 on rabbits skin.

3 - PSP 6022 PREPREGS

Impregnation of continuous fibers (tapes or fabrics), is very easy to realise with PSP 6022, particularly in solvent process with PSP 6022 M solution in MEK. Condensation rates of PSP 6022 M and PSP 6022 P have been choosed to give excellent tack and drape to prepregs, the prepolymers without solvent being very viscous or semi-solid at room temperature.

Long storage times are allowed for the prepregs by the stability of the resin at room temperature : several months storage at 25 °C does not affect the properties of the prepregs.

Incidence of polar solvents on mechanical properties has been checked and has been found as bad as expected, with a press cure cycle of 4 hrs at 200°C and 2 hrs at 250 °C under 1 MPa, and 16 hrs post cure at 250°C. DMF had been added in small quantities to a ceto-alcohol solution of PSP 6032 (quite similar to PSP 6022) before impregnation, and shear strength and flexural properties have been measured.

Test Temperature	DMF in solution (%)	Shear Strength (MPa)	FLEXURAL	
			Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)
25°C	0 %	90	1 800	135
	1 %	55	1 780	139
	5 %	47,5	1 570	120
250 °C	0 %	62	1 480	122
	1 %	52	1 700	132
	5 %	45	1 420	122

The tremendous loss of shear strength with as less as 1 % DMF in solution used for impregnation is probably explained by adsorption in carbon fiber, and this point the interest of non polar solvent solutions of which MEK is the most usual and less toxic. This is one of the reasons why SNPE had investigated modifications of the previous PSP resins: PSP 6030 was soluble in methylpyridines, PSP 6032 and PSP 6022 N in 75/25 mixture of MEK and propanol, PSP 6022 M and PSP 6022 P in MEK.

Another reason was the problem of odor : PSP 6030 was unable to impregnation, and PSP 6032 and PSP 6022 N retained some non reactive pyridine derivatives which have been removed from PSP 6022 M and PSP 6022 P.

PSP 6022 resin may be also reinforced with chopped fibers (glass or carbon). It is easy to prepare glass thermoset molding compounds by mixing short fibers and PSP 6022 PC powder, or by powdering PSP 6022 PC on a mat. For short staple carbon fibers reinforced compounds it is better to impregnate continuous roving with PSP 6022 PC in hot melt process, and then cut the prepreg in the desired length.

4 - CURING OF PSP 6022 REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Details of processing conditions may depend of course on the type of resin (6022 M or P) , resin content, laying up configurations or apparatus. Typical schedules are given.

Press cure schedule

- heat the plates of the press at 200 °C
- put the cast form (opened on 2 sides), with wished number of plies between the plates; temperature of the cast form reaches 200 °C within about 10 to 15 minutes.

- put the top plate to contact, without pressure, to avoid air contact on the upper ply

- hold at 200 °C for 1 hr 30 to 1hr 45
- apply 1 MPa over 15 minutes
- hold for 1 hr 30 under 1 MPa
- heat to 250 °C and hold for 2 hrs at 250 °C under 1 MPa
- cool to 60°C under pressure.

For high temperature resistance, post cure of 4 hrs at 250 °C is recommended.

Typical properties are plotted in table 2

Bag molding schedule

A silicon bag is used to transmit pressure by means of pressurized air, on prepreg plies layed up in a cast form heated at 200 °C with a radiant panel. Pressure (0,4 to 0,5 MPa) is applied after 1 hr 45 min, and total heating is 8 hrs at 200 °C. There is no vacuum in the bag.

A post cure from 4 hrs to 16 hrs at 250 °C is recommended for high temperature resistance.

Typical properties of unidirectional laminates based on T300 and 6022 M or 6022 P (16 ply laminate, thickness 2 mm) are described in table 2.

Autoclave molding

Typical experiments are carried on 16 ply unidirectional laminates whose final dimensions were 30 cm X 30 cm X 2 mm. The arrangement in the vacuum bag is as follows.

- 1 - Sealant
- 2 - Vacuum bag
- 3 - Glass bleeder
- 4 - Dam : silicon RTV
- 5 - Non porous PTFE glass cloth
Glass cloth style 1581
Non porous PTFE glass cloth
Porous PTFE glass cloth (Du Pont Warlon 234 TF)
- 6 - Bleeder cloth : glass cloth style 1581
- 7 - Porous PTFE glass cloth (Du Pont Warlon 234 TF)
- 8 - Prepreg lay-up
- 9 - Plate with coated release agent

To mold standard T 300/6022 prepreg to 60 o/v laminate of 2 mm thickness, 4 plies of bleeder cloth (glass style 1581) and a 4 mm thickness dam are used.

In most experiments, vacuum was applied only at the edge of the bag, to maintain it tight. For processing study, there was inert gas (N₂ or Argon) flowing away in the bag; gas was preheated in the autoclave and volatils were partially trapped through style 181 glass fabric.

It seems also performant to apply a slight vacuum in the bag (50 to 100 mm Hg). Too much vacuum would result in too much flow, viscosity of the resin being very low at 200 °C.

Typical autoclave cure schedule is as follows :

- heat to 200 °C at 2°C /min
- hold at 200 °C for 1 hr (+ 15 min)
- apply 700 kPa over 15 minutes
- hold for 8 hrs under 700 kPa
- Cool to room temperature under pressure.

Post cure of 4 hrs to 16 hrs at 250 °C is necessary, depending high temperature resistance requested.

Other autoclave cure schedules have been found efficient, even with only 4 hrs at 200 °C under 700 kPa and 3 hrs post cure at 250 °C. Laminates may also be cured at 225 °C or 250 °C under pressure, for shorter times.

Typical properties are plotted in table 2 .

Molding compounds

Process used for chopped fibers reinforced PSP 6022 PC curing has been :

- 2 hrs at 225 °C under 6 MPa pressure, with glass short fibers
- 1 hr at 250 °C under 6 MPa pressure, with carbon short fibers

Post cure of 16 hrs at 225 °C or 250 °C is used to improve thermo-mechanical properties ; results are summarized in table 3.

Miscellaneous process

PSP 6022 reinforced with fibers or fabrics may also be cured in different ways : without any pressure, like for filament winding (typical cycle 9 hrs 180 °C, 8 hrs 200°C et 7 hrs 225°C with a low condensation PSP 6022 NP4 used in wet winding, and 1 h 100°C, 1 hr 150°C, 4hrs 200°C, 2 hrs 250°C with PSP 6022 used in a prepreg form) or for wrap-ping on a mandrel (4 hrs 200°C et 2 hrs 250°C).

Injection is very easy to realise with PSP 6022 P or PSP 6022 PC due to the rather slow reactivity of PSP 6022 at 150 °C - 180 °C and the low viscosity of the prepolymer at these temperatures. High performance reinforced composite materials have been prepared using this process (7) and important developments are expected for radomes or missile applications (multidirectional network impregnation).

5 - REINFORCED PSP 6022 PROPERTIES

Mechanical properties

PSP 6022 matrix reinforced laminates have mechanical performances as high as epoxy laminates (tables 2 et 4). Typical room temperature interlaminar shear strength is 90 MPa to 100 MPa for unidirectional carbon PSP 6022 composites and is only slightly affected by post cure. Cross plied and carbon or glass reinforced laminates give also satisfactory values.

Thermomechanical properties

Very high levels of mechanical properties have been found, up to 400°C, with unidirectional carbon reinforcement, as measured after 15 min at the test temperature (table 5) : flexural modulus does not change, flexural strength loss is 10 to 20 % at 350 °C and 400 °C and ILSS at 400 °C is 40 % of the value at room temperature. Good values are also obtained with glass fabrics (table 4). The incidence of cure cycle and post cure on thermomechanical properties is shown in table 2.

High thermomechanical performances are also measured on molding compounds, as shown in table 3 : flexural strength and modulus of 23 % fiber volume 3 mm carbon fibers reinforced PSP 6022 PC remain unchanged, to a high level, from 20 °C to 300 °C.

The thermostructural and electromagnetic performances of glass reinforced PSP 6022 radomes has also been demonstrated at temperatures up to 400 °C (7) : dielectric constant is about 4.5 and loss tangent less than 2.10^{-2} from 20°C to 400°C.

Thermal aging

Measurements have been made on test samples, in air at 250 °C with unidirectional carbon T 300 reinforced PSP 6022. Loss of more than 20 % of shear strength at 20 °C and 250 °C begins to appear after 1000 hrs at 250 °C, even for laminates cured at 200 °C only, without post cure. Data are plotted on table 6. It seems that thermooxidative stability of T300 carbon fibers may have significant effect, as measured on unimpregnated fibers : fiber weight loss is 4 % after 1000 hrs at 250 °C, 8 % after 1500 hrs 13 % after 2000 hrs at 250 °C.

Good performances have also been observed with chopped T300/PSP 6022 PC molding compounds : 80 % of initial flexural properties are maintained after 5000 hrs at 200 °C (3 mm length carbon fibers, 23 % fiber volume).

Thermal and mechanical fatigue

It had been shown (1) that carbon reinforced PSP were not sensitive to cyclic thermal shocks (2000 cycles of 5 min 225°C/20°C).

Mechanical fatigue resistance has been examined on unidirectional T300/PSP 6022 laminates, with a flexural 3 points pulsated bending test at 25 Hz at 60 % of the ultimate flexural strength (0,9 % strain). Flexural strength and modulus remain unchanged after 107 cycles (there was about 10 % loss on a T300/epoxy laminate properties tested for comparison).

Moisture resistance

The extraordinary moisture resistance of carbon/PSP laminates, previously reported for HTS/PSP 6030 (1), has been confirmed on carbon T300/PSP 6022 unidirectional laminates; there is only a slight loss of interlaminar shear strength at 200°C after 1000 hrs in boiling water on laminates cured in autoclave at no more than 225°C, with no post cure. Moisture pick up is 0.7 % after 100 hrs immersion in boiling water (8hrs 200°C curing, 16 hrs post cure at 225°C).

Flammability properties

They have been measured on selected material composites of PSP 6022 resin and various reinforcements, and have been previously reported (2) (3) (5).

Resistance to combustion has been determined by LOI, the limiting oxygen index, which is the minimum oxygen concentration required to support flaming combustion. LOI of neat cured resin in ASTM-D 2863-70 test conditions is 26 %, and LOI of various reinforced PSP 6022 laminates are plotted in table 8: LOI of less than 1 mm thickness 60 % vol fabric/PSP 6022 laminates are about 40 % with Kevlar, 70% with carbon 100 % with E glass (sizing A 1100).

The smoke generating properties have been determined in an NBS chamber (2) and a similar apparatus with a radiant heating of 2.5 W/cm² (5); as it can be seen in table 9, glass and carbon reinforced PSP 6022 give impressive performances in terms of very low smoke emission in both flaming and non flaming conditions.

The toxicity of smoke gases emitted from glass reinforced PSP resins has been found especially low by measurement of gas composition in NBS chamber (2) and stated as apparent lethal concentration 50 by pyrolysis of glass reinforced laminates (2).

Energy released from PSP 6022 reinforced laminates exposed to radiant energy levels of about 5 W/cm² have been found very low, specially with carbon reinforcement (5).

Protection against flame had been also evaluated under severe conditions, with a plasma gun exposure at about 1800°C (0.5 kw/cm²) during 0.5 min on glass fabric reinforced PSP resin or at about 3000 °C (2 kw/cm² gas speed Mach 0.2-0.3) during 2 min, on Genin Thermoproof fabric/PSP laminate: PSP matrix appeared more performant than other resins in the same conditions (3).

6 - CONCLUSION

PSP 6022 appear to be very high performance resins for use as matrix of reinforced composite materials; high mechanical properties very high thermomechanical characteristics up to 400 °C and good thermostability at 250 °C are similar to those of the best polyimide reinforced materials, moisture resistance is outstanding, and very good flame resistance, low smoke emission and very low toxicity of pyrolysis products are some of the most important benefits of the PSP systems.

The most surprising and interesting properties are perhaps that the PSP 6022 resins are very easy to use : prepolymers are soluble in MEK with no need of high boiling point polar solvents like with other thermostable systems , resulting in no void laminates with cure cycles at only 200°C under 500 to 700 kPa pressure. Long shelf life prepregs of good tack and drape are prepared very easily in solvent (MEK) or non solvent process, and PSP 6022 resins seem to be specially favourable systems for injection processes.

PSP 6022 M, 6022 P and 6022 PC resins are produced in pilot scale in SNPE facilities, for solvent and non solvent impregnation and injection.

Industrial unidirectional or fabric prepregs (glass, carbon, or other) are available at competitive prices. Other types of resins , specially designed for particular applications, may be prepared easily in pilot scale.

The high performances of PSP 6022 should account for an active interest of their use in many applications, where temperature moisture or flame capabilities are required, like in aircrafts, missiles, automobiles...

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PSP PREPOLYMER SYNTHESIS

TABLE 1
TYPICAL PROPERTIES OF
PSP 6022 NEAT RESINS

Physical properties :

Density 1.14

Thermal expansion coefficient $60 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$

Mechanical properties

Flexural strength	100 MPa
Flexural modulus	2600 MPa
Tensile strength	40 to 50 MPa
Tensile modulus	2800 MPa

Thermal degradation

Thermal aging in air

Weight loss $\sim 2\%$ after 1 200 hrs - 250°C

Electrical properties

Dielectric constant 2,3 to 2,5
 Loss tangent $0.9 \cdot 10^{-2}$ ($\sim 9\text{GMz}$).

Table 2
 TYPICAL THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES
 OF UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES T300/6022 (2 mm THICKNESSES)

Molding	Flexural (20°C)		Interlaminar Shear strength		
	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	at 20°C : 250°C : 300°C (MPa)		
<u>Press molding</u>					
T300/6022 N	1560 (16)	122 (16)	90 (16)	63 (16)	60 (16)
T300/6022 P	-	-	77 (0)	56 (0) 54 (16) 61 (16a)	-
<u>Bag molding</u>					
T300/6022 N	1790 (16a)	110 (16a)	83 (16a)	63 (16a)	55 (16a)
T300/6022 P	1850 (4)	125 (4)	96 (4)	-	46 (4) 54 (16)
T300/6022 M	1850 (4)	124 (4)	104 (4)	-	46 (4) 54 (16)
<u>Autoclave molding</u> (at 200°C)					
A1:T300/6022 N	1920 (0)	111 (0)	90 (0) 94 (2)	61 (0) 61 (2)	-
A2:T300/6022 N	-	-	100 (0) 100 (1)	38 (0) 58 (1)	-

Post cure : (0) - no post cure
 (n) - n hrs at 250 °C
 (n-a) - n hrs at 225 °C.

Cure cycles

Press : 4 hrs 200 °C + 2hrs 250°C under 1 MPa after 90 min
 Bag : 8 hrs 200 °C under 500 KPa after 105 min
 Autoclave : A 1 : 7 hrs 200 °C + 2 hrs 225 °C under 1 MPa after 60 min
 A 2 : 9 hrs 200 °C under 1 MPa after 60 min.

TABLE 4
THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES (MPa) OF
PSP 6022 N REINFORCED WITH GLASS E FA-
BRIC STYLE 181 / TF 910

Temperature	Flexural (MPa)		Shear strength (MPa)
	Strength	Modulus	
20 °C	500	26 400	39
150 °C	470	27 200	38
200 °C	440	25 000	38
250 °C	390	24 800	35
300 °C	340	24 800	31

Cure cycle : - 4 hrs - 200°C + 2hrs 225 °C under 1 MPa
- post cure at 225 °C

Nota : With curing at 250 °C, without post cure, ILSS > 45 MPa.

TABLE 5
THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES (MPa) OF
UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON T300/PSP 6022N

Temperature	Flexural (MPa)		Shear Strength (MPa)
	Strength	Modulus	
20 °C	1 560	122 000	90
250 °C	1 610	127 000	63
300 °C	1 420	126 000	60
350 °C	1 200	127 000	42
400 °C	1 410	127 000	35

Cure cycle : - 4 hrs 200 °C + 2 hrs 250 °C under 1 MPa
- post cure 16 hrs 250 °C.

TABLE 6
THERMAL AGING PROPERTIES
OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON T300/PSP 6022 N

Press cure : 4 hrs 200 °C + 2 hrs 250 °C under 1 MPa after 90 min, and post cure of 16 hrs at 250 °C

Bag cure : 8 hrs 200 °C under 500 kPa after 105 min, no post cure.

Time at 250°C	Flexural				Interlaminar Shear strength (MPa)		Δ M (%) carbon dry
	Strength (MPa)		Modulus (MPa)		20 °C	250 °C	
	20°C	250 °C	20 °C	250 °C			
<u>Press cure</u> <u>with PC</u>							
0 h	1 400	1 300	107	105	85	64	-
250 h	1 100	1 200	93	95	84	65	- 1 %
500 h	-	-	-	-	79	63	- 1 %
1000 h	1 000	1 000	89	103	62	56	- 4 %
1500 h	-	-	-	-	60	40	- 8 %
							(-13 % at 2000 h)
<u>Bag cure with</u> <u>no PC</u>							
0 h	-	-	-	-	85	36 (64)*	
250 h	-	-	-	-	72	58	
500 h	-	1 690	-	123	69	55	
1000 h	-	1 330	-	112	67	46	
1500 h	-	-	-	-	46	34	
							*(after 24hrs

TABLE 7
MOISTURE RESISTANCE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL
CARBON T 300/PSP 6022 N

Interlaminar Shear strength in MPa.

Aging tests are made on test samples. Moisture test is boiling water immersion

Cure cycles (autoclave) : A1 : 7 hrs 200 °C +2 hrs 225 °C under 1 MPa after 60 min

A2 : 9 hrs 200 °C under 1 MPa after 60 min.

Cure cycle	Initial ILSS (MPa)		Moisture aging (hrs, in boiling water)							
	20°C	200°C	48 hrs		100 hrs		500 hrs		1 000 hrs	
	20 °C	200°C	20 °C	200°C	20 °C	200°C	20°C	200°C	20°C	200°C
<u>A1 -no post cure</u>	88	60	91	48	84	51	87	49	89	50
<u>A1 - PC 1 hr 250 °C</u>	92	60	89	55	86	61	-	-	-	-
<u>A2 - no post cure</u>	98	37	91	41	100	33	-	-	-	-
<u>A2 - PC 1 hr 250 °C</u>	100	57	89	60	89	55	-	-	-	-

TABLE 8

LIMITED OXYGEN INDEX OF PSP 6022

REINFORCED LAMINATES

Reinforcement and sizing	Number	or plies et thickness:	Cure cycle	LOI	
				Vertical	Horizontal
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
Glass E Fabric-181 style (satin 8)	:	:	:	:	:
A 1100 sizing	: 4	: 0.8 mm	: P.C.	: 100 %	: 99 %
" " " "	:	:	:	:	:
" " " "	: 15	: 2.9 mm	: P.C.	: 100 %	: 100 %
" " " "	:	:	:	:	:
TF 910 sizing	: 4	: 0.8 mm	: P.C.	: 61 %	: 54 %
" " " "	:	:	:	:	:
" " " "	: 4	: 0.8 mm	: No P.C.	: 57 %	: 52 %
" " " "	:	:	:	:	:
" " " "	: 10	: 2.0 mm	: No P.C.	: 80 %	: -
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
Carbon T 300 fabric - satin 5 (290g/m ²)	:	:	:	:	:
- (epoxy sizing)	: 4	: 1.0 mm	: P.C.	: 69 %	: 62 %
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
Kevlar 40 fabric -181 style (170 g/m ²)	: 5	: 1.0 mm	: P.C.	: 39 %	: 37 %
" " " "	:	:	:	:	:
" " " "	: 15	: 3.0 mm	: P.C.	: 54 %	: 54 %
" " " "	:	:	:	:	:
" " " "	:	:	:	:	:

NOTA - cure cycle : 4 hrs at 200 °C et 2 hrs at 250 °C under 10 bars pressure;
P.C. (post cure) : 4 hrs at 300 °C with glass and carbon
14 hrs at 250 °C with Kevlar.

Fiber content : about 60 % volume.

TABLE 9
SMOKE DENSITY OF PSP 6022
REINFORCED LAMINATES

Radiant eneyy - 2.5 W/m²

Flaming : with pilot flame ignition.

Reinforcement and sizing	Number of plies	Thickness	Cure cycle	Maximum Specific Optical Density			
				(Dm) Sample vertical	Sample horizontal		
				Flaming: Non flaming	flaming: Non flaming		
Glass E fabric-181 style A1100	4	0.8 mm	P.C.	15.0	4.5	1.1	1.1
"	4	0.8 mm	No P.C.	21.0	13.0	7.0	1.2
TF 910	4	0.8 mm	P.C.	36.0	16.0	3.0	0.35
"	4	0.9 mm	No P.C.	24.0	13.0	4.6	2.0
"	15	2.9 mm	P.C.	39.0	22.0	7.9	17.0
Carbon t 300 fabric satin 5 (290 g/cm ²)	4	1.0 mm	P.C.	17.0	1.4	0.7	3.0
Kevlar 49 fabric - 181 style (170 g/m ²)	5	1.0 mm	P.C.	105.0	101.0	32.0	48.0
	15	3.0 mm	P.C.	231.0	318.0	163.0	172.0

NOTA - Cure cycle : 4 hrs at 200 °C et 2 hrs at 250 °C under 10 bars pressure
P.C. (post cure) : 4 hrs at 300 °C with glass et carbon
14 hrs at 250 °C with Kevlar.

Fiber content : 60 % to 65 % volume.